

Development of a Transfer Standard for DC Power Quality Reference Systems

G. Frigo and M. Agustoni

Lab. of Electr. Energy and Power, Swiss Federal Institute of Metrology
Bern-Wabern, Switzerland (email: guglielmo.frigo@metas.ch).

Abstract—Most renewable energy sources are operated in direct current (DC) and require dedicated inverter to be integrated in the power system. This results in loss of rotational inertia as well as degradation of the power quality (PQ) indices. A promising alternative is represented by low-voltage DC grids, whose standardization though is still incomplete. Reference systems are being developed for DC metering and DCPQ, but their validation requires inter-laboratory comparison. To this end, we propose the design and preliminary characterization of a transfer standard for DCPQ measurements. The obtained results confirm the reliability of the proposed architecture, that guarantees a worst-case power uncertainty of 1 % over the frequency range from DC to few tens of kHz.

Index Terms—Microgrid, DC grid, Power Quality, Inter-Laboratory Comparison, Reference System

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern power systems are characterized by an ever-increasing penetration of renewable energy sources (RES) and distributed generation (DG). These resources are typically operating in direct current (DC) and thus require power converter to be interconnected to the traditional alternating current (AC) grid [1], [2]. Such a paradigm change is expected to produce a significant reduction of the carbon footprint, but also to cause a reduction of rotational inertia and a degradation of power quality due to the disturbances introduced by the switching of the converters' circuitry [3], [4]. In this sense, low-voltage DC (LVDC) grids represent a promising solution in order to fully and efficiently exploit these resources [5], [6].

The LVDC standardisation is currently focusing on safety aspects (e.g. installation, wiring, voltage and current levels), but is still lacking in terms of metrology infrastructure. In particular, the measurement of power quality (PQ) indices in LVDC represents an open issue from a methodological and technological point of view [7]–[9]. In order to address these challenges, the European Metrology Program for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) has launched a new project, named *DC grids* [10], whose aim is to develop and characterize reference systems for DC metering and DCPQ. In this preliminary stage of the research, the DCPQ phenomena are limited to DC ripple, reproduced as single-tone AC components superposed to a stable DC level. In the absence of a pre-defined standard framework, plausible variation ranges have been set for DC and AC components. More precisely, DC component levels range from 18 to 1000 V and from 1 to 800 A for voltage and current, respectively, whereas AC components have a maximum relative magnitude of 10 % and a spectral bandwidth

up to 150 kHz. In terms of target performance, the DCPQ reference system shall guarantee an accuracy of 0.1 % for the DC component and a measurement capability index of 10 for the AC component.

In order to meet these stringent requirements, the reference system relies on a synchronous generation and re-acquisition of the test waveforms. Such measurement procedure allows for post-processing the re-acquired waveforms and accurately identify the reference values for DC and AC parameters. In particular, the project aims at developing three reference systems at METAS, VSL, and PTB, namely the Swiss, Dutch and German National Metrological Institute (NMI), respectively. The three systems shall not be identical and adopt different measurement chains to generate the test waveforms (a preliminary description of the METAS and VSL implementation is given in [11], [12]). In the absence of fully traceable measurements of DCPQ indices, a rigorous characterization of the three reference system relies on an inter-laboratory comparison in a pre-defined set of test conditions. Given the complexity of the reference systems and the logistic difficulties related to their displacement, the best solution consists in a round-robin comparison of a transfer standard, namely a reference meter for the measurement of DCPQ indices.

Hence, it is important to design and develop a transfer standard whose accuracy is sufficient to discriminate the performance of the different reference systems. In this sense, this paper describes a possible implementation of a transfer standard relying on a high-accuracy industrial controller and discusses the possible sources of uncertainties inherent in the measurement chain. By knowing in advance the frequency response of the transfer standard, it will be also possible to assess the effect of DCPQ events on power and energy measurements.

More precisely, we present the development and preliminary characterization of the DCPQ transfer standard. In this regard, we particularly focus on the synchronized acquisition of voltage and current test waveforms. Such an aspect represents one of the most stringent implementation challenges, in terms of instrument transformer and triggering mechanism. In this context, we carry out a characterization of the transfer standard performance in the presence of DC ripples within its Nyquist bandwidth, and we derive a preliminary uncertainty budget in terms of estimated AC power. The obtained results confirm the flexibility and reliability of the proposed architecture and indicate the possible spaces for improvement.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the hardware and software architecture of the transfer standard. In Section III, we describe the reference system and the measurement setup. Section IV presents the performance characterization and discusses the uncertainty contributions and still open issues in DCPQ measurements. Finally, Section V provides some closing remarks and outlines the next steps of the research activity.

II. THE METAS TRANSFER STANDARD

The METAS transfer standard consists of a NI cRIO-9068 (National Instruments, Austin, US-TX), i.e. an embedded industrial controller equipped with a Linux Real-Time (RT) Operative System (OS) and a re-configurable Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) board. More precisely, the cRIO-9068 relies on a 667-MHz dual-core ARM Cortex-A9 (Arm Holdings, Cambridge, GBR) processor, and a Xilinx Artix-7 (Xilinx, San Jose, US-CA) FPGA board. In the proposed architecture, the FPGA is responsible for the triggering and acquisition process, whereas the RT controller processes the acquired waveforms in order to identify the DC and AC component parameters.

For this analysis, the cRIO-9068 has been programmed in LabVIEW 2020 Real-Time via a dedicated Ethernet board, compatible with the IEEE Std 802.3 (Gigabit Ethernet) and characterized by a communication rate of 100 Mbps. In this way it is possible to establish a bi-directional communication with the host computer for programming the controller and retrieving in real-time the measurement results.

The cRIO-9068 is equipped with a voltage input module NI 9215. The proposed architecture relies on the assumption that the transfer standard has access to the low-voltage output of the instrument transformers of the reference systems. In this way, it is possible to characterize the entire measurement chain of the reference systems and not only their generation units.

The NI 9215 consists of four differential channels with an input range of ± 10 V and allows for simultaneously sampling with a cumulative maximum rate of 100 kHz. The four input channels are characterized by a resolution of 16 bits and a noise RMS level lower than $350 \mu\text{V}$. The Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) relies on a successive approximation register, and is preliminary calibrated in METAS laboratories with an accuracy of 0.05 % over the frequency range $[0, 50]$ kHz. In more details, the input channels are organized in two independent pairs: the first two channels (in the following referred to as *ai0* and *ai1*) responsible for the acquisition of voltage and current test waveforms, respectively and the remaining channels (*ai2* and *ai3*) devoted to the respective trigger signals. This allows for independent analysis of the voltage and current channels as well as for acquiring non-synchronous or single-channel events or disturbances.

In the present implementation, the FPGA provides the digitizer clock and manages the triggering of the different channels. This guarantees a deterministic and repeatable performance of the acquisition stage. In particular, the sampling rate is set equal to 50 kHz. As soon as a trigger channel detects a rising edge transition, an occurrence function activates the

corresponding analog input for the test waveform. In this regard, it should be noticed that the synchronization uncertainty is equal to one tick of the FPGA 40-MHz onboard clock, i.e. nearly negligible in the considered application scenario.

The acquired waveforms are stored in two dedicated First-In-First-Out (FIFO) queues (in the following referred to as V-FIFO and I-FIFO, respectively). A third FIFO queue (T-FIFO) stores the number of ticks elapsed between two consecutive acquired samples. This register is intended for debugging procedures and allows for verifying the sampling rate precision and stability over long periods of time.

On the RT side, the samples are extracted from V- and I-FIFO in consecutive non-overlapping intervals of 200 ms. The choice of the window length is inspired by the traditional configuration of PQ meters for AC grids, yielding a frequency resolution of 5 Hz. In this preliminary stage of the research, the reporting rate is also set equal to 5 Hz, since the considered test conditions are stationary and do not involve any transient or discontinuity. Nevertheless, the proposed software and hardware architecture is capable of modifying the window length and the reporting rate, with the only limitations represented by the buffer depth of the FIFO queue and the maximum update rate equal to the adopted sampling rate.

The 200-ms intervals are further processed in order to extract the parameters of interest. First, we identify the DC RMS value as the statistical mean. Once subtracted it, we compute the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) and define the AC component parameters as the amplitude, frequency and phase associated to the maximum spectral peak. In order to improve the resolution, the frequency granularity is increased by a factor 10 via zero-padding. Moreover, a Hanning weighing function is applied to reduce long-range spectral leakage contributions from the negative image component and possible other spurious components.

In this regard, it is important to notice that the proposed estimator, yet simple and technically unsophisticated, benefits from the controlled operating conditions of the transfer standard. In this calibration context, it is reasonable to assume that the disturbances and interferences are minimized and the test waveform parameters are known (accurately) in advance. It is then possible to reproduce a condition of quasi-synchronous sampling, where the considered interval contains an integer number of periods of the AC component of interest. Nevertheless, the deployment of an estimator based on interpolated DFT is envisioned in the next steps of the research in order to account for possible inconsistencies between the generated test waveforms and the aforementioned assumptions.

III. MEASUREMENT SETUP

The performance of the transfer standard are characterized by means of the METAS reference system for DC energy and DCPQ, whose hardware architecture is shown in Fig. 1.

The system consists of two parallel and independent channels for voltage and current waveforms that supply the corresponding input channel of the device under test (DUT, gray-shaded boxes). For this analysis, instead, the transfer

Fig. 1. METAS reference system for DC energy and DCPQ meters: voltage and current measurement chain in (a) and (b), respectively.

standard is connected directly to the analog outputs of the instrument transformers, i.e. the voltage divider and the current sensor. In this way, it is possible to compare the estimates of the transfer standard with the parameters identified by the reference system.

In the voltage channel, the measurement chain consists of two branches. In the upper one, a function generator (FGEN) reproduces the user-defined test waveform, and outputs also a trigger signal locked to the lowest AC component. A high-bandwidth amplifier (V-AMP) suitably increases the voltage level of the test waveform, that is supplied to the DUT, and simultaneously re-acquired via the lower branch. A voltage divider scales down the voltage level, compatibly with the analog front end of a high-precision digitizer (DIG). It is worth noticing that the acquisition process is driven by the same trigger signal output by the FGEN. The acquired waveform is then processed via a non-linear fitting routine in order to extract the DC and AC parameters of interest.

Similar considerations hold also for the current channel, apart from two main aspects. First, the FGEN uses two channels to drive separately a current source (I-SRC) and a high-bandwidth transconductance amplifier (I-AMP) for the DC and AC components, respectively. Second, the voltage divider is replaced by a high-precision fluxgate current transducer.

In more details, the FGEN consists of a Keysight 33512B Waveform Generator (Keysight Technologies, Santa Rosa, CA), equipped with two independent output channels characterized by a bandwidth and an output range of 20 MHz and 10 V, respectively. The 33512B allows for locking the phase of the two output channels and provides also an external trigger functionality with a resolution of 4 ns.

As per the V-AMP, we use a Trek PZD700A Amplifier (Advanced Energy, Denver, CO) with output range and bandwidth of 700 V and 150 kHz, respectively. The adjustable gain is set equal to the nominal value (1:200) with a declared accuracy of 0.1 %. The voltage sensor consists of a passive resistive divider, designed and manufactured at the METAS workshops,

with a maximum input range of 1 kV and a fixed ratio of 300:1. The divider has been calibrated in DC at METAS laboratories with a ratio accuracy of 10 ppm.

The DIG is a PicoScope 5443D (Pico Technology, St Neots, UK) equipped with 4 independent input channels, and characterized by sampling rate, input range and vertical resolution equal to 500 kHz, 1 V, and 14 bits, respectively.

The I-SRC consists of two DeltaElektronika SM15-400 power supplies (De Zuidhoek, Zierikzee, NL) connected in parallel for an overall output range of 800 A, with a resolution of 0.4 A and an accuracy of 0.2 A. The I-AMP, instead, is a Clarke-Hess 8100 transconductance amplifier (Clarke-Hess Communications, Medford, NY) with an output range and bandwidth of 100 A and 100 kHz, respectively. In the 20 A range (i.e., the one used for this analysis), the transconductance accuracy is not larger than 0.1 %.

Finally, the current sensor is a DaniSense DS600ID Current Transducer (DaniSense A/S, Taastrup, DK) whose input range and bandwidth are 1000 A and 500 kHz, respectively, with a nominal primary current of 900 and 600 A for DC and AC components respectively. Based on the DC calibration results, the fixed gain of 1500:1 has an accuracy of 15 ppm.

IV. PERFORMANCE CHARACTERIZATION

The performance characterization aims at defining the frequency response of the proposed transfer standard. At this stage of the research, the main objective is to assess the capability of accurately quantifying the power associated to a DC ripple over a large bandwidth ranging from few tens Hz up to the Nyquist rate of the transfer standard (i.e., 25 kHz). For this analysis, we consider test waveforms modelled as:

$$x(t) = a_{AC} \cdot \cos(2\pi f_{AC}t + \varphi_{AC}) + \eta_{DC} \quad (1)$$

where η_{DC} is the DC component, whilst a_{AC} , f_{AC} and φ_{AC} represent the amplitude, frequency and initial phase of the single-tone AC component. In this regard, it should be noticed that the initial phase is defined with respect to the rising edge of the trigger signal, that accounts for the time reference of the entire measurement setup.

For the sake of brevity, the present analysis considers a limited set of test conditions. The DC component is fixed to 200 V and 100 A for the voltage and current case, respectively. In a similar way, the AC component amplitude and phase are set equal to 20 V and 0 rad in the voltage case, and 8 A and $\pi/2$ rad in the current case. The frequency, instead, varies between 10 Hz and 20 kHz with a logarithmic scale. For each considered configuration, we acquire 1000 consecutive intervals of 200 ms and characterize the measurement errors on each parameter in terms of mean and standard deviation. The first one is a systematic contribution and can be compensated, whereas the second one accounts for the estimation uncertainty.

a) Device calibration: First of all, we have calibrated the input channels $ai0$ and $ai2$ within the range $[0, 3]$ V, i.e. the expected variation range of the signal output by the voltage divider and the current transducer. The calibration

Fig. 2. Calibration results of the NI 9215 input channels in the presence of pure DC voltage component ranging from 0 to 1 V: systematic errors (a) and measurement uncertainty (b).

is performed in DC in order to guarantee the traceability to the realization of the volt in METAS laboratories. By assuming a linear behaviour of the ADC in the presence of AC components (as suggested by the NI 9215 specifications), we can reasonably state that the major uncertainty contribution is related to the noise introduced by the measurement chain and to the processing routine. In this regard, Fig. 2 illustrates the calibration results in terms of systematic and random contributions in (a) and (b), respectively. The two channels present a different yet strongly correlated behavior, with a worst-case uncertainty of 40 ppm (cover factor $k = 2$).

b) Waveforms' power quality: We evaluated the quality of the acquired test waveforms in order to quantify the level of noise and distortion introduced by the amplifier and sensor stages. For this analysis, we considered two metrics: the Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) computed over the first 50 harmonics (or up to the highest harmonic frequency lower than the Nyquist rate), and the Signal-to-Noise-and-Distortion (SINAD) ratio. For each test configuration, we computed the RMS value of THD and SINAD over 1000 consecutive 200-ms intervals. In this regard, Fig. 3 represents the THD and SINAD as function of the AC component frequency in the voltage and current channel in blue and red, respectively.

In the voltage case, it is interesting to observe a significant deterioration of the THD (reflected also in the corresponding SINAD) for input frequencies larger than 1 kHz. A possible motivation could be individuated in the parasitic capacitance effects of the voltage divider, that may introduce non-linear distortion of the output signal. In this sense, a more detailed characterization of the divider performance in the AC domain is envisioned. The current case, instead, is characterized by a nearly frequency independent behavior. The lower SINAD is motivated by the inefficient exploitation of the current transducer input range and by the higher quantization noise. In the considered configuration, the AC component amplitude of 8 A is converted in 4.267 mV, acquired with a fixed vertical resolution of 610 μV .

In summary, both the channels guarantee a worst-case THD around 2 %, whereas the SINAD do not fall below 25 and 18 dB for the voltage and current case, respectively.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) and Signal-to-Noise-and-Distortion (SINAD) as function of frequency in (a) and (b), respectively.

c) Estimates' distribution: Based on the aforementioned noise and distortion levels, it is reasonable to expect that the estimated parameter values doesn't distribute normally. In order to verify this assumption, Fig. 4 presents the quantile-quantile plots of the amplitude estimates for an AC component frequency of 100 Hz. In both the voltage and the current case, the estimations confirm the deviation of the data values from a nominal Gaussian distribution. A significant deviation is noticeable on the left-hand tail that proves to be longer and heavier than the right one. Based on these considerations, the traditional uncertainty definition relying on the estimates' standard deviation may result inappropriate. Consequently, in the following we define the uncertainty bounds associated to the different estimated quantities based on the 95-th percentile of the corresponding cumulative distribution functions.

d) Bode diagram: Based on the estimates of AC component amplitude, frequency and phase, it is possible to derive the Bode diagram of the proposed transfer standard. In this regard, Fig. 5 represents the frequency response of the voltage and measurement chain in terms of gain and delay in (a) and (b), respectively. The vertical bars denote the confidence intervals as deduced by the parameter estimation uncertainties.

In general, it is worth noticing an uncertainty deterioration proportional to the AC component frequency. This phenomenon can be related to two main motivations. On one side, the corresponding degradation of THD and SINAD (particularly, in the voltage channel). On the other side, the rapidly decreasing number of samples per period as the AC component frequency increases. Indeed, the simple spectral estimator -

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Quantile-quantile plot for the amplitude estimates in the voltage and current case in (a) and (b), respectively. For this analysis, the frequency was set equal to 100 Hz.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Bode diagram of the proposed transfer standard in terms of gain and delay as function of the AC component frequency in (a) and (b), respectively. The vertical bars represent the uncertainty with a cover factor $k = 2$.

Fig. 6. Blue circles: uncertainty on the estimated active power as function of the AC component frequency. Red solid line: linear regression model.

currently implemented in the device - is significantly affected by leakage effects that become more and more relevant as we approach the Nyquist rate.

Looking in more detail at the Fig. 5a), the voltage gain is remarkably linear and close to the nominal value up to the kHz range where it follows an exponential trend. A similar yet strongly non-linear trend is noticeable in the current gain, whose divergence from the nominal value begins already at 500 Hz. In the worst case, the asymmetric variation ranges for voltage and current channel are equal to $[-2, +4] \%$ and $[-6, +4] \%$, respectively.

In Fig. 5b), instead, the delays follow a cubic trend. Despite the use of different amplification and sensor stages, it is then possible to accurately compensate the frequency dependent delay of the two channels and thereby align voltage and current waveforms up to a worst-case uncertainty of few hundreds of μs in the kHz range.

e) *AC power uncertainty*: As a final step, we gather together the previously discussed contributions to derive an uncertainty budget for the active power measurements. In this regard, Fig. 6 illustrates the relative uncertainty as function of the AC component frequency. First, we considered the propagation of the different uncertainty contributions related to the module calibration and frequency response. Then, we fitted a linear regression model (red solid line), whose formulation can be written as follows:

$$U_{pow} = 4.151 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot f_{AC} \quad (2)$$

The resulting goodness of fit is quantified by a remarkable coefficient of determination, R^2 , which is equal to 99.83 %.

It is interesting to observe how the uncertainty does not exceed 1 % over the whole considered frequency range. Given the challenging measurement conditions (limited ripple of high DC component) and the simplicity of the spectral estimator, this result represents a promising starting point for the development a traceable and accurate transfer standard for DC energy and DCPQ reference systems.

f) *Computational complexity*: In view of a further improvement, the most challenging aspect is represented by the limited computational resources of the FPGA board. In its current implementation, the device utilizes only 40 % of the

total slices, namely 13 % of the registers and 24 % of the look-up tables. In terms of memory and processing capabilities, more than 70 % of RAM blocks are still available, whereas the computation charge for the DSP units is nearly negligible (0.5 %). In this sense, there is significant space for enhancement both in terms of interval length and preliminary processing already at FPGA level.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented the design and preliminary characterization of a transfer standard for inter-laboratory comparison of DC energy and DCPQ reference systems.

From the hardware point of view, the transfer standard relies on a National Instrument cRIO-9068, an industrial controller equipped with a FPGA board and a Linux RT controller. The first one guarantees a deterministic control of the acquisition process, whereas the second one is responsible for identifying the DC and AC parameters of interest.

From the software point of view, the parameter identification adopts a spectral estimator based on a zero-padded DFT. Despite its simplicity, the proposed approach benefits from the controlled test conditions, namely the quasi-synchronous sampling and the compensation of all the systematic contributions inherent in the different measurement chain components.

We have carried out a detailed characterization of the transfer standard metrological performance. In particular, we have analyzed the noise and distortion levels due to the generation and re-acquisition of the test waveforms, and we have defined the device response as function of the AC component frequency in terms of gain and delay. Based on these results, we could derive a preliminary uncertainty budget of the active power associated to DC ripple events.

The obtained results confirm the potential of the adopted hardware and software architecture and allow for identifying possible space for enhancement. In this sense, the future steps of the research activity will focus on the compensation of the sensor non-linear response (i.e., voltage divider and current transducer) and on the optimization of the spectral estimator in order to reduce leakage and noise contributions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This project (20NRM03 DC grids) has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. K. Bose, "Power electronics, smart grid, and renewable energy systems," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 105, no. 11, pp. 2011–2018, 2017.
- [2] M. Paolone, T. Gaunt, X. Guillaud, M. Liserre, S. Meliopoulos, A. Monti, T. Van Cutsem, V. Vittal, and C. Vournas, "Fundamentals of power systems modelling in the presence of converter-interfaced generation," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 189, pp. 1–33, 2020.
- [3] X. Xiao, A. J. Collin, S. Z. Djokic, S. Yanchenko, F. Möller, J. Meyer, R. Langella, and A. Testa, "Analysis and modelling of power-dependent harmonic characteristics of modern pe devices in lv networks," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 1014–1023, 2017.

- [4] G. Frigo, A. Derviškić, Y. Zuo, and M. Paolone, "Pmu-based rocof measurements: Uncertainty limits and metrological significance in power system applications," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 68, no. 10, pp. 3810–3822, 2019.
- [5] J. M. Guerrero, J. C. Vasquez, J. Matas, L. G. de Vicuna, and M. Castilla, "Hierarchical control of droop-controlled ac and dc microgrids—a general approach toward standardization," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 58, no. 1, pp. 158–172, 2011.
- [6] D. Kumar, F. Zare, and A. Ghosh, "Dc microgrid technology: System architectures, ac grid interfaces, grounding schemes, power quality, communication networks, applications, and standardizations aspects," *IEEE Access*, vol. 5, pp. 12 250–12 256, 2017.
- [7] G. Crotti, A. D. Femine, D. Gallo, D. Giordano, C. Landi, M. Luiso, A. Mariscotti, and P. E. Roccato, "Pantograph-to-ohl arc: Conducted effects in dc railway supply system," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 68, no. 10, pp. 3861–3870, 2019.
- [8] A. D. Femine, D. Gallo, D. Giordano, C. Landi, M. Luiso, and D. Signorino, "Power quality assessment in railway traction supply systems," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 69, no. 5, pp. 2355–2366, 2020.
- [9] A. Bracale, P. Caramia, G. Carpinelli, P. De Falco, and A. Russo, "Comparison of dc electric arc furnace chaotic models for power quality indices assessment," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 57, no. 6, pp. 6713–6721, 2021.
- [10] H. van den Brom, "Standardisation of measurements for DC electricity grids," International Electrotechnical Commission, Tech. Rep., 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.euramet.org/research-innovation/search-research-projects/details/project/standardisation-of-measurements-for-dc-electricity-grids/>
- [11] G. Frigo and J. Braun, "Measurement setup for a dc power reference for electricity meter calibration," in *2022 International Conference on Harmonics and Quality of Power (ICHQP 2022)*, 2022, pp. 1–6.
- [12] H. Van den Brom, Z. Marais, and R. van Leeuwen, "Testing of dc electricity meters with broadband conducted electromagnetic disturbances," in *2022 International Conference on Harmonics and Quality of Power (ICHQP 2022)*, 2022, pp. 1–6.